

Diplomatic Missions Develop Rules And Regulations

البعثات الدبلوماسية تطور نظام وقواعد

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Abstract

Diplomatic relations have enjoyed the care of Islamic Sharia, like all aspects of public and private human life, to be poured into a mold of sophistication and splendor in behavior and behavior, and woven to lay the foundations of respect and peace. These protocols, which humanity took thousands of years to establish, apply, adopt and impose as etiquette regulating the work of ambassadors, messengers and official envoys; It was formulated by the Noble Qur'an and the noble Prophet's guidance as an integrated sentence. By extrapolating the history of diplomacy from ancient times until today, we know the extent to which man is keen to adhere to this type of relationship in which the public is mixed with the private and the international with the personal, and how much he congratulated people in the eras that were ruled wisely and diplomatically and how much they broke into the covenants of rudeness and harshness. In Islam, diplomacy appears to be a crucifixion daughter of a text and a spirit. There is hardly an unanimous diplomatic rule that deviates from the provisions of Islamic law. While diplomacy took hundreds of years to appear as it is today, of transcendence and pomp; It was born in Islam with complete pillars as it was enacted and applied by the Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, and his companions and caliphs, and the Muslims gained as a result the respect and appreciation of enemies before friends. In light of this, the researcher who called it (Diplomatic Missions Evolution of a System and Rules) tried to present an objective vision of the phenomenon of the development of the diplomatic system and its rules, as it identifies the problem of the study in the need to adhere strongly and the importance of adhering to it without any specification, manipulation or condition, as it aims to invest and benefit from it in issues Establishing, contracting, and facilitating the education and service of foreign international relations, God willing. The research took the analytical aspect: in which the practical material is collected, extrapolated, interrogated, deduced patterns, and determined classifications to arrive at result.

Keywords: diplomatic missions, evolution, system. Rules

ملخص الدراسة:

حظيت العلاقات الدبلوماسية بعناية الشريعة الإسلامية شأنها كشأن كل نواحي الحياة الإنسانية العامة والخاصة لتأتي مسكوبة في قالب من الرقي والبهاء في السلوكيات والتصرفات، ومحبوكة بما يرسى دعائم الاحترام والسلام. هذه البروتوكولات التي استغرقت البشرية آلاف السنين لتأسيسها وتطبيقها وتعمدها وتقرضها كأداب سلوك ناظمة لعمل السفراء والرسل والموفدين الرسميين؛ قد صاغها القرآن الكريم والهدي النبوي الشريف جملة متكاملة مُحكمة. وباستقراء تاريخ الدبلوماسية منذ عهود قديمة حتى اليوم عرفنا إلى أي مدى حرص الإنسان على الالتزام بهذا اللون من العلاقات التي يمتزج فيها العام بالخاص والدولي بالشمسي، وكم هنئ الناس في العهود التي حُكمت بحكمة ودبلوماسية وكم شقوا في عهود الغلاظة والغلاظة. أما في الإسلام فتنبو الدبلوماسية ابنة صليبية له نصًا وروحًا. ولا تكاد قاعدة دبلوماسية أجمع عليها تخرج عن أحكام الشريعة الإسلامية. وفيما احتاجت الدبلوماسية لمئات السنين لتنبو على ماهي عليه اليوم من التسامي والأبهة؛ فإنها ولدت في الإسلام مكتملة الأركان حيث سنّها وطبقها النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم وأصحابه وخلفاؤه، وجنى المسلمون جراءها احترام وتقدير الأعداء قبل الأصدقاء.

في ضوء ذلك، حاول الباحث الذي سميتها (البعثات الدبلوماسية تطور نظام وقواعد) لتقديم رؤية موضوعية لظاهرة تطور النظام الدبلوماسي وقواعده، إذ تحدد مشكلة الدراسة في حاجة التمسك بشدة وأهمية الالتزام بها دون تخصيص ولا كيد ولا شرط، حيث تهدف إلى استثمارها والإفادة منها في قضايا التأسيس والتعبيد وتيسير تعليم وخدمة العلاقات الدولية الخارجية إن شاء الله. وقد أخذ البحث الجانب التحليلي: الذي يتم فيه جمع المادة العملية واستنقاؤها واستنباط الأنماط وتحديد التصنيفات وصولاً لنتائج.

الكلمات المفتاحية: البعثات الدبلوماسية، تطور، نظام، قواعد

recognized by the state with which it wishes to establish diplomatic relations. The commentators require that the recognition on which diplomatic relations are established should be de jure and not merely tacit or de facto, and that relations that arrive or continue without express recognition are not considered regular diplomatic relations, and the persons to whom they are entrusted do not enter. It is within the scope of diplomatic envoys in the true sense of the word. The state is just agents for the state to take care of its interests with other countries.

However, we believe that if this opinion can be accepted in the case of the establishment of a new state, then there is no place to abide by it in the event of a change in the system of government in an old state between which diplomatic relations are already established with other states.

The mission of foreign envoys to the country ends with the change of the regime, and they must submit new credentials, if it is seen that relations between their countries and the country they are dispatched to will continue. This procedure, that is: presenting credentials in the name of the new head of state, is in itself, according to what has been the case, an official recognition of the new regime and is sufficient for the continuation of diplomatic relations in their first status without the need for an explicit independent recognition of the new government.

Extent of the state's right to exercise diplomatic representation:

If the exercise of diplomatic representation is a right of the state, does this correspond to a duty imposed on states to enable each other to use this right? Or in other words: Is the state obligated to accept diplomatic envoys of other countries? And that she exchanged representation accordingly, so she sends envoys from her? In fact, there is no legal obligation in this regard; The subject is related to good relations more than abstract law. However, a state's refusal to establish diplomatic relations with other states results in its isolation and remaining outside the scope of the group of states, and consequently excluding itself from the sphere of application of positive rules of international law, which is not in its interest at all and would impede its advancement and support its international status.

Based on this, from the point of view of the international community, it can be said that there is a duty among civilized states that imposes on them the acceptance of diplomatic representatives for each other, unless there are serious motives calling for them to take a different approach.

In this regard, Article Two of the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations states that "establishing diplomatic relations between states and dispatching permanent diplomatic missions shall be by mutual consent." Article VIII of the Havana Agreement concluded between the American states states that "no state can decide to send representatives diplomats before other countries without a previous agreement between the two parties".

The second requirement: the mission of diplomatic missions:

Duties of the diplomatic mission:

The diplomatic mission is the communication tool between the sending state and the receiving state. Its tasks are summarized as follows:

First - Representing the country sending the mission before the country accredited to it, and this representative task is assumed by the head of the mission himself, or whoever takes his place in his absence, or they take his position, and the manifestation of this mission is to attend parties and official receptions to which foreign diplomatic representation bodies are invited, and perform the courtesy visits that took place. It is customary to perform it on various occasions and the like.

Second - Negotiating with the government of the sending state on all matters of interest to the sending state, and working to bring the two states closer together on common issues. This negotiation is usually between the head of the mission and the foreign minister of the receiving state or his representative.

Third: Tracking incidents in the receiving state and informing the sending state of all that it is interested in being aware of of these incidents. The head of the mission seeks the assistance of political, commercial, military and other attachés under his administration, in reconnaissance of various affairs, but he must not resort to obtaining the information he wants to other than honorable methods. Illegal.

Fourth: Monitoring the implementation by the sending state of its obligations before the receiving state, and interfering with the foreign minister of the first state whenever a breach of these obligations occurs. However, neither the head of the diplomatic mission nor any of its members may intervene directly before the local authorities.

Fifth - Protecting the nationals of the country sending the mission if there is an attack on them or their money. However, the head of the mission is not allowed to interfere with the government of the country unless it is proven that those of them claiming harm have exhausted all the normal methods allowed by the laws of the country without succeeding in obtaining his right.

Sixth: Strengthening good relations and establishing and consolidating economic, cultural and scientific relations between the sending state and the receiving state.

Seventh - In addition to the above, the diplomatic mission shall carry out the administrative tasks assigned to it by the laws and internal regulations of its country regarding its nationals in the sending country. Such as registering births and deaths, making marriage contracts, marking passports, and the like. It is customary to entrust these works to the consuls under the supervision of the head of the diplomatic mission, or the consuls initially undertake them in an original capacity, as we will explain when studying the consular representation.

Duties of diplomatic envoys:

Members of the diplomatic mission, when performing their duties, have duties that he must observe before the country they are sent to, in consideration for the dignity of this country on the one hand, and in compliance with the legitimate boundaries of their mission on the other. The diplomatic envoy:

First - Respecting the constitution of the country he is sent to and the system of government there, refraining from doing any act that disrespects the government or the prevailing systems, and never interfering in the private affairs of the state or any of its authorities. And the diplomatic envoy.

Second - He shall not at all provoke disturbances or disturbances for any purpose whatsoever or contribute to any revolutionary movement or encourage a coup or political campaign against the actions of the existing government or criticize these actions on his part or support one party against another, and in general he shall avoid All interference in the internal political alliances.

The diplomatic envoy must also not act in any way that may shock or hurt the feelings or beliefs of the people, and he must respect the traditions and religions followed, even those that may seem strange in comparison with the traditions and beliefs of the people to which he belongs. For this reason, he must not, as much as possible, fail to attend public parties that are held for national or national occasions He called for it, for his retardation might sometimes have the meaning of humiliation if he had no justification.

In the field of courtesies, the diplomatic envoy must be very careful to do them, contributing to happy events such as birthdays, marriages, or the like, and comforting in calamities, whether those befall the head of the state or his family or a man of government, or disasters befall the people such as an earthquake Or fire, flood, etc.

Even during crises that may occur in the relations between the envoy's country and the envoy's country, the envoy must not be affected in his personal conduct by the atmosphere of these crises, so he does not diminish his respect for the head of state and does not deviate from following the rules of behavior and courtesy imposed on him by the duties of his representative mission. Every act of a diplomatic envoy in contravention of his foregoing duties permits the sending state to consider his persona non grata, and to request his state to summon him or to direct him, when necessary, to leave its territory. Diplomatic relations towards the state they are dispatched to, and it stipulates in Article 41 that "Without prejudice to the privileges and immunities assigned to them, persons who enjoy these privileges and immunities have a duty to respect the laws and regulations of the state they are accredited to, and they also have a duty not to interfere in the internal affairs of this state. Dealing with all official matters entrusted to the mission by the government of the accredited country with or through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the country receiving it, or with any other agreed ministry The mission headquarters may not be used in a way that is inconsistent with the mission's tasks as stated in the provisions of this agreement or other The general rules of international law or the special agreements in force between the adopting country and the country accredited to it.

The third requirement: the formation of diplomatic missions:

The strength of the diplomatic mission

The size of the diplomatic mission: The nature of the tasks related to diplomatic representation and the multiplicity and complexity of the work subordinated to these tasks require that they be carried out by more than one person. Therefore, the countries decided that each of them sends a group of people to carry out its diplomatic missions, each of whom undertakes one of these tasks under the leadership of a responsible person who is considered the original representative of his country to the countries to which he is delegated. This group, including its head, will be the so-called diplomatic mission. As for the number of people who are included in this group, it varies from one mission to another, according to the amount and importance of the interests that link the country sending the mission to the country sending it to. It is left to the sending country to estimate this, and to determine the number of persons it deems necessary to send to carry out its diplomatic missions, and various other related or subordinate activities. Special needs for the official work of the mission justify this, and when it became clear that sending such a number is often for the purpose of carrying out another activity outside the normal diplomatic activity, which contradicts the objectives of diplomatic representation and with the interests of the country to which the mission is sent, the opinion has been settled that this country has the right to Demands that the number of delegates be reduced to a reasonable limit, and refuses to accept more than this limit. The Vienna Convention, in its eleventh article, acknowledged this provision by saying: "In the absence of an express agreement between the two countries on the number of members of the mission, the receiving State may require that this

number remain within reasonable and customary limits in view of the circumstances and conditions prevailing in this State and the special needs of the mission. Likewise, the receiving state, within the same limits and on the condition of non-discrimination, may refuse to accept employees of a certain category.

Formation of the diplomatic mission:

The group of persons comprising or affiliated with a diplomatic mission includes the following categories:

1. Head of Mission: He is the person entrusted by the State to represent it and head its diplomatic mission to a particular country.
2. Members of the mission: they are the officials appointed by the sending country of the mission to work with the head of the mission, and they are of three sects as follows:
 - a. Diplomatic staff: They are the persons who hold diplomatic ranks and are entrusted with the assistance and supervision of the head of the mission, to carry out various diplomatic tasks. These include advisers and secretaries of different ranks and attaches of different qualities. These employees, including the head of the mission, are called members of the diplomatic corps.
 - b. Administrative and technical staff: They are those who undertake the administrative and technical work of the mission, such as archivists, account managers, money changers, clerks and the like.
 - c. Mission employees: They are the people who carry out service, maintenance and guarding work in the diplomatic mission house, such as brushes, couriers, telephone workers, guards and the like.
3. Accountable servants: They are the people who work in the domestic service of the head of the mission or its members. The differentiation between these different functions is important, as we will see later in terms of the terms of appointment and acceptance first, and in terms of the immunities and privileges they enjoy in the second.

Ranks of Heads of Diplomatic Missions

Arrangement of envoys according to their ranks: In the foregoing, the issue of progress and prominence in official receptions and receptions has been mentioned in disputes and even bickering between diplomatic envoys of various countries, especially the major countries, and the abuse that these disputes and quarrels led to. To the relations between countries whose envoys compete for the advancement of one another, an abuse that sometimes amounted to the threat of severing relations or war, as we referred to the interest of countries in the Vienna Conference in 1810 AD and Mutter x La Chapelle in 1818 AD in placing The ranking system for the heads of diplomatic missions is inevitably due to these problems and disputes.

The Vienna list, in its preamble, referred to the previous situations by saying: (And, desiring to avoid the problems that were often presented and which will be presented in the claims of primacy among the diplomatic envoys, the commissioners of the countries preceding the signing of the Paris Treaty have agreed to the following texts, and consider it their duty to invite Other heads of state have to follow the same system.

These texts, as previously mentioned, divided the diplomatic envoys into three categories, one after the other, and then a fourth category was added to these three categories under the Axe-La Chapelle Protocol. It is what has been established by the work between countries during the long years before and after them, and therefore there is no justification for modifying it or replacing it with another system.

Accordingly, Article 14 of the last agreement stipulates dividing the heads of diplomatic missions into three ranks as follows:

First- The rank of ambassadors and delegates of the Pope at the rank of apostolic delegate. These are the highest ranked envoys and are directly dependent on the head of the state who is delegated to them, and they have the right to contact him and request to meet him whenever there is a need, and they enjoy the greatest hospitality and honor in their reception and in the official ceremonies to which they are invited. A diplomatic mission headed by an ambassador is called an "embassy."

Second - The rank of envoys extraordinary, ministers plenipotentiary, and the pope's delegate at the rank of Apostolic Nuncio. These are followed in rank by their predecessors, but they are also dependent on the head of the state they are delegated to as representatives of their head of state, and the diplomatic mission headed by one of these is called (the commission.)

Third - the rank of those in charge of business. These, unlike the previous two categories, are considered envoys by the foreign minister of their country to the foreign minister of the country to which they are delegated, and accordingly they do not have the right to communicate directly with the head of the state they are accredited to. This arrangement has its impact in terms of primacy and ceremonies, so each rank precedes the next rank in terms of progress in official parties and interviews, and the precedence is among members of the same rank according to seniority, and it is calculated from the date on which the envoy notifies the country to which he is delegated news of his official arrival or from the date of submitting his credentials according to the system The practice in this country, provided that this system is applied in general and without discrimination between the delegates. The amendments that may be made to the credentials of the head of the mission without leading to a change in his rank shall have no effect on his role in the lead.

The custom in Catholic countries was for the Pope's envoy and the Vatican's envoy, other men of the diplomatic corps, to come forward. The Vienna Convention recorded this custom in the third paragraph, Article 16, stipulating that the previous arrangement would not be affected by it. Each country must take into account that the procedures to be followed in receiving the heads of diplomatic missions are the same for each class. With the exception of matters relating to preeminence and ceremonies, no distinction is made between the heads of diplomatic missions according to their rank, as they all have the same competencies, have the same duties, and enjoy the same rights, immunities, and privileges. In the past, it was the practice not to send envoys of the rank of ambassadors except to the major royal states, but this tradition has no value at the present time. Work is underway to agree between the two countries that exchange diplomatic representation on the rank of each other's envoy. Most likely they are both of the same rank, but there is nothing to prevent them from being of two different ranks.

Acting Acting Persons:

It may happen that the position of the head of the diplomatic mission becomes vacant and cannot be filled for some time, or circumstances prevent the head of the mission from carrying out his duties, and it is customary in such a case that the sending country appoints to temporarily manage the mission's work (a chargé d'affaires on behalf of). And that this appointment be notified to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the sending country, and the chargé d'affaires on behalf other than the chargé d'affaires who is the original permanent head of a diplomatic mission.

However, if the position of the head of the mission becomes vacant without the sending state notifying the receiving state of the choice of a charge d'affaires on behalf, then it is assumed, according to what has been the work, that the mission's management shall be taken over temporarily by the diplomatic employee directly next in the order of the head according to the diplomatic list of the mission, until his state takes the position of the head of the mission Formal action in this regard.

Appointment of diplomatic missions

The speech deals with the following in the appointment of diplomatic missions:

First - A statement of the conditions for appointment to diplomatic posts.

Second - A statement of the procedures for appointment to these jobs.

Conditions for appointment to diplomatic posts:

Who may be appointed to diplomatic posts: Each country usually determines the conditions that must be met by whoever is appointed to its diplomatic posts, and this is mostly through special legislation that it sets for this purpose and includes all the provisions regulating its representative body. The state has complete freedom in this field, whether in determining the conditions it requires for those who occupy its diplomatic functions, or in choosing the persons to whom it is entrusted with these functions. The basic principle is that the diplomatic missions of the state are assumed by persons specialized in these tasks, who progress in diplomatic posts from the beginning until they reach their summit, and thus acquire through long practice and practice in different circumstances and environments the experience and expertise necessary for the right diplomat. This category of people who are cut off from diplomacy is called professional diplomats: but the state often uses in diplomatic functions and tasks, in addition to professional diplomats, people from other professions with qualifications such as judges, literature or medical professionals b or the lawyer, as university professors and military men; It also often attaches to its diplomatic missions people with specialization in various non-political affairs to carry out tasks related to their specialization, such as commercial, cultural, military attachés, journalists, etc.

We will mention what is followed regarding appointment to Arab diplomatic posts when studying the diplomatic system of the United Arab Republic in Chapter Eight of the current section, content with referring to the general provisions on which each country organizes its diplomatic apparatus.

There is no doubt that this highlights the character and identity of Islam; Where he made the fulfillment of treaties a matter attached to the dignity of man, whether Muslim or infidel, without discrimination, and for the Muslim in this a fortiori, the Almighty said: {Those who fulfill the covenant of God and do not break the covenant}. The agreements and treaties that are established between states are a list of mutual trust that the parties must maintain and take care of them seriously, especially those who have the character of Islam, and what a non-Muslim has been able to do and adhere to, based on human values كما فكيف بمن يؤمن بالله ورسوله والرسول فينا أسوة حسنة قال تعالى: {وَمِنَ أَهْلِ الْكِتَابِ مَنْ إِنْ تَأْمَنَهُ بِقِطَارٍ يُؤَدُّ إِلَيْكَ}، كما في God's revelations for a small price, those will have their reward with their Lord, for God is swift in reckoning. {

The third requirement: the positive and negative development of the relationship of the Islamic nation with the international community

وفي الإطار الفلسفي فإن القرآن الكريم طرح عددًا من القيم التي تحكم صلة الدولة المسلمة بغيرها من الدول انطلاقًا من آية الحجرات: {يَا أَيُّهَا النَّاسُ إِنَّا خَلَقْنَاكُمْ مِنْ ذَكَرٍ وَأُنْثَىٰ وَجَعَلْنَاكُمْ شُعُوبًا وَقَبَائِلَ لِتَعَارَفُوا إِنَّ أَكْرَمَكُمْ عِنْدَ اللَّهِ أَتْقَاكُمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ عَلِيمٌ خَبِيرٌ}. It is clear from the context of the noble verse that acquaintance is the goal of this diversity that exists in the world, and it must be said that acquaintance is an origin in the white relations between humans on earth, when the relationship is based on the basis of the human family, before it is exposed to any negative or positive development.

In many verses, the Holy Qur'an indicated that the difference between people is approved, and considering that difference is praiseworthy if it was within the framework of diversity and respect.

And when the relations between human beings develop positively and negatively; The Holy Qur'an presented another value for the relations between individuals and states, and did not accept the Muslim to continue in the language of forgiveness while others practice aggression and fighting. Rather, it presented multiple realistic options that vary according to the reality of the international community and the development of relations between the Islamic state and its counterparts in the world.

The positive context was not limited to acquaintance, but rather presented a series of positive relationships that begin with acquaintance, then competition, then cooperation, then brotherhood, then compassion, then altruism. On the negative side, it also begins with acquaintance, but it develops down to the stampede until it finally reaches fighting and confrontation. This fact can be read in the Book of God by following the wise Quranic commandments in this way.

Positive development:

-Familiarity: {And We have made you peoples and tribes, that you may know one another {.

-Competition: {In that let the competitors compete. {.

Cooperation: {And cooperate in righteousness and piety, but do not cooperate in sin and aggression {.

Compassion: {Severe against the infidels, merciful among themselves. {.

Altruism: {And they prefer themselves, even if they have a need {.

Brotherhood: {The believers are but brothers, so make peace between your two brothers and fear God that you may be shown mercy. {.

Naturally, each of these values is linked to the corresponding behavior of the other and determines its position in the system of values within the framework of interrelationships.

Negative development:

On the other hand, these values are directed downward in order to confront disgraceful behaviors in which the other will exchange the nation's position on acquaintance and integration.

-Familiarity: {And We have made you into peoples and tribes that you may know one another. {.

Argumentation: {And do not argue with the People of the Book except with what is better, except for those who have wronged them {.

Reciprocity: {So whoever transgresses against you, transgress against him in the same manner as he attacked you {.

-Caution: {O you who have believed, beware of yours, so go forth steadfastly, or all of you go forth {.

-Ambush: {Say: "Wait, for I am with you among those lurking".

- الاستعداد: {وَأَعِدُّوا لَهُمْ مَا اسْتَطَعْتُمْ مِنْ قُوَّةٍ وَمِنْ رِبَاطِ الْخَيْلِ تُرْهِبُونَ بِهِ عَدُوَّ اللَّهِ وَعَدُوَّكُمْ} التدافع: {وَلَوْلَا دَفْعُ اللَّهِ النَّاسَ بَعْضَهُمْ بِبَعْضٍ لَفْتَنَتْ صَوَامِعُ وَبَيْعٌ وَصُلُواتٌ وَمَسَاجِدُ} .

Fighting: {And fight in the cause of God those who fight you, but do not transgress, for God does not like the aggressors {.

And so on; The natural relationship in Islam begins with acquaintance and then goes up or down according to the behavior of the recipient, and the matter is true of the relationship between individuals and the political reality between countries.

A conception of peaceful, white relations between the Islamic community and other societies based on the logic of "to get to know each other", and acquaintance is a white and common value, from which the development of relations, negative or positive, begins, which is the lowest of the positive ladder and the highest of the negative ladder. The Conclusion Sharia provided clear ways to build a relationship Within the framework of creed, for example, the Islamic creed is based on six pillars: belief in God, His angels, His books, His messengers, the Last Day, and Predestination.

Upon insightful observation, we find that faith in Islam is based on two pillars that are directly related to the good relationship with the other, where Islam commanded belief in all the prophets and the heavenly books, and this faith is the most wonderful entrance to building a culture of love and peace between the Muslim and the world, and building a positive constructive dialogue that serves everyone.

It is well known that belief in the prophets requires the necessity of respecting their guidance and light, and belief in the heavenly books inevitably requires respect for their teachings and guidance, positive interaction with the inherited ones, and building positive approaches between the Muslim and the followers of all the prophets.

The Noble Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, achieved these wonderful meanings in building a positive and balanced dialogue relationship, which was manifested in the city's constitution, in which he wrote what guarantees the rights of all residents of the city regardless of their religions, cultures and ethnicities. Religions wishing to learn about the tolerance of Islam and establish positive and constructive relations, and when a delegation of Christians from Najran came to him, he honored them and placed them in his honorable mosque, and they established a

time during which they eat and drink, and although they did not openly declare their entry into Islam and their belief in God and His Messenger and his religion, the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, continued their dialogue and honoring them. He called for them to be guided, and many of them came to him later as Muslims.

The culture of positive cooperation between people is repeated in every Surah in the Noble Qur'an, and the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, achieved it in the most complete way. Whoever made peace with him and my brother from his brother, and he gave the greatest example of brotherhood and compassion.

Results

The following is a brief summary of the most important findings of the study:

- Islam endorsed the principle of friendly relations between states, as well as mutual recognition of sovereignty between them. The study provided evidence for that from the Qur'an, Sunnah, the work of the nation and its history.
- Emphasizing that the origin of the relationship of the Islamic nation with other nations is peace and not war, and discussing opinions that went to the contrary.
- Indicating the development of awareness and practice of diplomatic issues throughout the history of the Rashidun Caliphate, the Umayyad Caliphate, the Abbasid Caliphate, and the successive states after that.
- Demonstrating the positive and negative development in Muslims' relations with the international community, and emphasizing the flexibility granted by Sharia texts in judging different countries according to their stances towards the nation in terms of justice and good neighborliness.
- Explanation of the legality of temporary diplomatic representation in Islam, and its support from the Qur'an and Sunnah, the work of the Islamic nation and the history of its countries.
- Explanation of the ruling on permanent diplomatic representation in Islam, and the evidence for this from the Book, the Sunnah, the work of the nation and its history, and a reference to the most important permanent ambassadors during the Muhammadan state.
- Devising the conditions for appointing ambassadors according to the guidance of the Qur'an and Sunnah, and trying to establish legal rules for choosing ambassadors, guided by the biography of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace.
- Studying the issue of modern cultural, military and commercial attachés, searching for their counterparts in Islamic history, and seeking ways to enhance their legitimacy by serving the nation in various aspects.
- Detailing the etiquette of ambassadors in Islamic jurisprudence, according to the implications of the Book, the Sunnah and the work of the nation, and an attempt to collect them in a systematic and objective framework.
- The principle of reciprocity is sanctioned by Islamic Sharia and today is governed by diplomatic norms, and the nation is commanded to abide by it in its diplomatic relations, and it is not permissible to abandon it except in the context of the real interest of the nation.
- The ambassador is commanded to be loyal to his homeland and to the land of his residence, and these interests may not contradict in friendly relations, but rather they complement and continue.
- The difference of beliefs should not prevent the establishment of correct relations. Diplomatic interaction is an earthly affair based on the apparent. As for the unseen, it is a heavenly affair and only God knows it, and the matter of reckoning people is entrusted to God Almighty.

Margins:

Classification and theory of social behavior: Towards a scientific framework for the study and development of human sociology. Muhammad Ziyad Hamdan. P.: 33. Modern Education House. 2015.

-Surah An-Nahl. Verse: 71.

-Surat Al Nisaa. Verse: 32.

-See: Arab Economic Integration and Industrial Coordination: An Analytical Study. Hamed Obaid Haddad. Journal of the College of Arts - University of Baghdad. Volume 2012, Issue: 99 (February 28, 2012). pp.: 640-660.

Compare Raoul Genet: Part 1 Clause 3-16, pp. 6-17.

On the positive side, jurisprudence calls *droit de légation actif*, and on the negative side, *droit se légation passif*.

See in detail the Pope's right to send and accept diplomatic representatives: Public International Law, 1960 edition, item 142-144.

Clause No. 229. Achioli No.: 111. Fonet, pp. 352-354.

See Genet in *Diplomacy and Diplomatic Law*, which includes a detailed presentation of the current situations in the various countries called lacking sovereignty and their exercise of the right of diplomatic representation. Part 2 Clause 561-620 p. 6-76.

This was similar to what was stipulated in the Damascus Charter, which was concluded between the United Arab Yemen Mutawakkilite Kingdom on March 8, 1958 and established the Union of Arab States to assume political representation. The consulate of the Federation abroad is one body in the cases where the Federation so decides (see Articles 6-8 of the Charter.)

See: Fushi 1-3, Item 667-1, p. 40 et seq.

Public International Law: Recognition of the State and the New Government and Its Image, Article 86, p. 164 et seq.

Compare Fauci: op. Item 664, p. 37. See Edition: 1948, Part One, pg. 691.

The Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations provided for the advanced tasks and listed them in five points, including its third article.

See: Bonfils: No. 681-683. Aquili 2: No. 1149-1152. Clause No. 232. Faunier: p. 365. Fauchy: No. 683 p 54.

mission diplomat

Chef de mission.

Membres de la mission.

Personnel diplomat.

Agents diplomates.

Personnel administratif et technique.

Personnel de service.

Domestiques privés.

The enumeration of all these persons who could be included in a diplomatic mission was mentioned in Article 1 of the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations.

See the above, p. 88.

Ambassadeurs.

Nonces.

Ambassade

Envoyés extraordinaires

Ministres plénipotentiaires

Internonces

Legation

Chargés d'affaires

Articles: 15-16 of the Vienna Convention.

Compare articles: 14 paragraphs 2 and 18 of the Vienna Convention.

This is stipulated in Article 15 of the Vienna Convention

See Genet, Part I, p. 267 et seq.

chargé d'affaires ad interim.

It is called en pied chargé d'affaires

Diplomates de carrière.

Compare to the foregoing on p. 24 - 27.

Surah Thunder. Verse: 20.

Surat Al-Imran. Verse: 75.

Surat Al-Imran. Verse: 199.

Surah Al-Hujurat. Verse: 13.

Surah. Verse: 48.

Surah Al-Hujurat. Verse: 13.

Surah Al Mutaffifin. Verse: 26.

Surah. Verse: 3.

Surah Al-Fath. Verse: 29.

Surah Al-Hashr. Verse: 9.

Surah Al-Hujurat. Verse: 10.

Surah Al-Hujurat. Verse: 12.

Surah Al-Ankabut. Verse: 46.

Surat elbakara. Verse: 194.

Surat Al Nisaa. Verse: 101.

Surah At-Tur. Verse: 31.

Surat Al-Anfal. Verse: 6.

Surah Hajj. Verse: 40.

Surat elbakara. Verse:

Resources and References

- [1]. Classification and theory of social behavior: Towards a scientific framework for the study and development of human sociology. Muhammad Ziyad Hamdan. P.: 33. Modern Education House. 2015.
- [2]. Arab economic integration and industrial coordination: an analytical study. Hamed Obaid Haddad. Journal of the College of Arts - University of Baghdad. Volume 2012, Issue: 99 (February 28, 2012). pp.: 640-660.
- [3]. Compare Raoul Genet: Part 1 Clause 3-16, pp. 6-17.
- [4]. See in detail the Pope's right to send and accept diplomatic representatives: Public International Law, 1960 edition, item 142-144.
- [5]. See Genet in Diplomacy and Diplomatic Law, which includes a detailed presentation of the current situations in the various countries called lacking sovereignty and their exercise of the right of diplomatic representation. Part 2 Clause 561-620 p. 6-76.
- [6]. This was similar to what was stipulated in the Damascus Charter, which was concluded between the United Arab Yemen Mutawakkilite Kingdom on March 8, 1958 and established the Union of Arab States to assume political

representation. The consulate of the Federation abroad is one body in the cases where the Federation so decides (see Articles 6-8 of the Charter.)

- [7]. See: Fushi 1-3, Item 667-1, p. 40 et seq.
- [8]. Public International Law: Recognition of the State and the New Government and Its Image, Article 86, p. 164 et seq.
- [9]. Compare Fauci: op. Item 664, p. 37. See Edition: 1948, Part One, pg. 691.
- [10]. The Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations provided for the advanced tasks and listed them in five points, including its third article.
- [11]. See: Bonfils: No. 681-683. Aquili 2: No. 1149-1152. Clause No. 232. Faunier: p. 365. Fauchy: No. 683, p. 54.
- [12]. mission diplomat
- [13]. Chef de mission.
- [14]. Membres de la mission.
- [15]. Personnel diplomat.
- [16]. Agents diplomates.
- [17]. Personnel administratif et technique.
- [18]. Personnel de service.
- [19]. Domestiques privés.
- [20]. The enumeration of all these persons who could be included in a diplomatic mission was mentioned in Article 1 of the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations.
- [21]. Ambassadeurs.
- [22]. Nonces.
- [23]. Ambassade
- [24]. Envoyés
- [25]. Ministres plénipotentiaires
- [26]. Internonces
- [27]. Legation
- [28]. Chargés d'affaires
- [29]. Articles: 15-16 of the Vienna Convention.
- [30]. Compare articles: 14 paragraphs 2 and 18 of the Vienna Convention.
- [31]. This is stipulated in Article 15 of the Vienna Convention
- [32]. See Genet, Part I, p. 267 et seq.
- [33]. Chargé d'affaires ad interim.
- [34]. It is called en pied chargé d'affaires
- [35]. Diplomates de carrière.,.